

Effect on addition of BAP and NAA Growth Regulator on Gamborg (B5) Tissue Culture Medium to Produce Callus

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Plant tissue culture is one of popular biotechnology technique that used the totipotency of a plant. Plant tissue culture technique is defined as an aseptic way to culture plant tissue or organ under defined physical and chemical environment in vitro (Thorpe, 2007). The success in carrying out plant tissue culture is depend on various aspect such as availability of nutrition, the presence of potential explant and the enviromental factor including pH, temperature and light frequencies. Some research on plant tissue culture used MS (Murashige and Skoog) as their basic culture medium. MS medium considered as a general plant tissue culture medium because MS medium contained primary nutrition for plants. Another culture medium such as Gamborg (B5) medium is used to culture fabaceae family. B5 (Gamborg) media contained macro stock solutions, micro stock solutions, Fe stock solutions, vitamin stock solutions, Myo-Inositol, glucose obtained by compacting gelatin, 70% alcohol (Gusmiaty, 2023) . To enhance callus in plant tissue culture, some researchers modified the culture medium by adding growth regulator. Plant Growth Regulator defined as non-organic compound that does not act as nutrient for plant but in a small amount regulate plant physiological process (Umami, 2012). Most research these day used BAP and NAA growth regulator to enhance callus in plant tissue culture combined with MS medium. This article aim to analyze the differrent between BAP and NAA added to B5 medium instead of added to MS medium to produce callus.

Plant tissue culture medium has big impact on the growth and development of the plants. The substrate or medium should be compatible with the explant being propagated and the growing target of the culture. Plant tissue culture mostly used as a technique to produce callus, callus is a tissue consists of irregularly shaped parenchyma cells that form on wounded or cut areas of a plant. This callus can develop from various plant parts, including leaves, stems, nodes, or tubers, when grown on agricultural media (Almemary, 2020). Previous study about producing callus mostly used modified MS. In a study by Nofiana (2017) using MS combine with some concentration of BAP and in a study by Wahyuni (2021) using MS combine with some concentration of NAA. MS defined as general medium for plant tissue culture, MS medium was made to culture mangrove, and then perfected by controlling organic salt contained in the medium. Despite, MS was made to culture mangrove, the macro element contained in MS can be used to support the growth of another plants culture. Meanwhile in a study by Buchori and Karjadi (2008) they used B5 to culture soy bean suspension this medium uses a low concentration of NH_4^+ , because concentrations higher than 2 mM inhibit soybean cell growth. The phosphate concentration given to the media is mM, Ca^{2+} between -4 mM, and Mg between 0.5-4 mM.

Tissue and organ is easier to proliferate from a callus. The growth regulator that involved in producing callus is auxin and cytokinins (Aprilia et al, 2022). Callus induction can be done by using the right ratio of NAA and BAP. In previous research by Pramono et al. (2021) they used BAP and NAA combination in some different concentration to produce callus of *Nigela sativa*. BAP (Benzyl Amino Purine) is considered the most effective cytokinin when compared to others. NAA is more effective than IAA because it is not degraded by IAA oxidase or other enzymes, making it longer-lasting. Additionally, NAA is more stable in the presence of oxidase and light (Nurzaman,

2005). Amin et al. (2003), as cited by Hayati et al. (2010), note that callus induction is determined by a balanced ratio of auxin and cytokinin, requiring the correct combination to achieve optimal callus formation.

Gamborg (b5) medium is rarely used for plant tissue culture, it happened because gamborg medium is not basic medium like MS. In the research that has been done by Yan et al (2009) comparing some basal medium to cultured *Allium chinensis* showed that the used of B5 medium has the highest callus induction of 49%. Meanwhile, the percentage of callus induction using MS is only 39%. B5 has potential to induce highest callus than another culture medium because B5 has Lower NO₃/NH₄⁺ ratio in B5 medium stimulated callus initiation and growth (Luciani et al., 2006). According to Hidayat et al (2020) The B5 medium (Gamborg) has a reduced level of organic nutrients, making it well-suited for growing soybeans. In general, B5 medium, which has a lower organic nutrient content compared to MS, creates more favorable conditions for the cells of specific plant species.

The addition of BAP (6-Benzylaminopurine) and NAA (Naphthaleneacetic Acid) in tissue culture has been extensively studied for its effects on plant growth and development. BAP is a cytokinin that promotes cell division and differentiation, leading to increased shoot growth and root development. In contrast, NAA is an auxin that stimulates cell elongation and differentiation, contributing to enhanced root growth and leaf formation. The combination of these plant growth regulators (PGRs) in tissue culture media can significantly impact the growth and regeneration of plant tissues. For example, a study on the tissue culture of pineapple found that the addition of NAA and BAP in specific concentrations (1-3 mg/L NAA and 1-5 mg/L BAP) enhanced shoot growth and callus proliferation, while higher concentrations of NAA (>3 mg/L) suppressed shoot growth even in combination with BAP (Zulkarnain and Neliyati, 2017)

The optimal combination of BAP and NAA in tissue culture media can vary depending on the specific plant species and the desired outcome. For instance, a study on the tissue culture of Kepok Kuning banana found that the combination of 4 ppm NAA and 8 ppm BAP resulted in the highest number of shoots and leaves, while the combination of 7 ppm NAA and 5 ppm BAP produced the highest number of roots and plantlet height (Andany and Ratnasari, 2023). Similarly, a study on the tissue culture of Smooth Cayenne pineapple found that the combination of BAP 3 mg/L and NAA 2 mg/L produced the highest number of shoots per explant from embryogenic callus (Dahniar and Elvavina, 2022). These findings highlight the importance of optimizing the combination of BAP and NAA in tissue culture media to achieve the desired outcomes for plant propagation and genetic engineering research.

The combination of these plant growth regulators (PGRs) in B5 basal medium can significantly impact the growth and regeneration of plant tissues. For example, a study on the tissue culture of *Polianthes tuberosa* found that the addition of different concentrations of BAP and NAA to the B5 basal medium resulted in varying levels of root formation and shoot growth (Naz et al., 2012). The optimal combination of BAP and NAA in B5 basal medium can vary depending on the specific plant species and the desired outcome. For instance, a study on the tissue culture of *Polianthes tuberosa*

found that the combination of BAP and NAA in specific concentrations (e.g., 1 mg/L NAA and 3 mg/L BAP) enhanced root formation and callus induction, while higher concentrations of NAA (>1 mg/L) suppressed root formation even in combination with BAP (Soni, et al., 2011). Similarly, another study on the tissue culture of *Polianthes tuberosa* found that the combination of BAP and NAA in specific concentrations (e.g., 1 mg/L NAA and 2 mg/L BAP) produced the highest number of shoots and leaves (Anjani and Ratnawati, 2023).

There are synergistic effects when combining BAP (6-Benzylaminopurine) and NAA (Naphthaleneacetic Acid) with other plant growth regulators in B5 medium. Combining BAP with GA (Gibberellic Acid) in B5 medium has been shown to enhance shoot multiplication in *Paulownia*. Higher concentrations of BAP (3 or 4 mg/L) in combination with 0.1 mg/L NAA and 0.1 mg/L GA resulted in valuable shoot multiplication but decreased estimated growth values (Salem et al., 2022). The combination of NAA and BAP with other hormones like IBA (Indole-3-Butyric Acid) and Kinetic (6-Furfurylaminopurine) has been found to enhance root formation and shoot growth in various plant species. For example, a study on the tissue culture of *Mentha piperita* found that the combination of NAA and BAP with IBA and Kinetic improved root formation and shoot growth compared to using individual hormones (Wijaya et al., 2022).

Plant tissue culture is a popular biotechnological technique that exploits the totipotency of plant cells, defined as the ability to culture plant tissues or organs aseptically under controlled physical and chemical conditions *in vitro*. The success of this technique depends on various factors, including nutrient availability, suitable explant presence, and environmental conditions such as pH, temperature, and light frequencies. MS (Murashige and Skoog) medium is commonly used due to its comprehensive nutrient composition, while Gamborg's B5 medium, which contains lower organic nutrients, is often used for specific plant families like Fabaceae. Researchers often enhance callus induction by adding plant growth regulators such as BAP (Benzyl Amino Purine) and NAA (Naphthaleneacetic Acid). These regulators, in appropriate combinations, significantly influence callus formation and subsequent plant tissue growth and regeneration. Although B5 medium is less frequently used than MS, it has shown higher callus induction rates in certain studies due to its specific nutrient composition. Overall, the choice of culture medium and the addition of growth regulators play crucial roles in optimizing plant tissue culture outcomes.

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